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Svetovanje in izobraževanje, dr. Andrej Raspor, s. p.
Dolga Poljana 57
5271 Vipava, SI Slovenija
E-pošta: zalozba.perfectus@gmail.com

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Odgovorna urednika

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BALKANSKI POTOVNI PLAKATI XX. STOLETJA

Svitlana Pryshchenko <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3482-6858>¹

Povzetek:

Namen: Avtor obravnava popotniški plakat kot orodje oglasnega komuniciranja in sestavino kulturne podobe Balkana. Posebno zanimiva je medkulturna interakcija zaradi širjenja informacijskega prostora, kulturnega in umetniškega razvoja ter krepitve evropskih integracijskih procesov.

Metodologija: Študija temelji na sistemsko-strukturalni, primerjalni in sociokulturni metodi. Avtorica je za analizo vizualizacijskih sredstev in likovno-slogovnih značilnosti popotniškega plakata v 20. stoletju uporabila kronološko-žanrski princip.

Rezultati in zaključki: Članek se osredotoča na analizo stopenj stilizacije plakatov od skoraj realizma do formalizacije in generalizacije. Vizualno razmišljanje v oglaševanju uporablja grafične veščine, metode vizualne umetnosti in stilistiko evropske umetnosti. Primerjava popotniških plakatov pokaže, da ljudski motivi v sedemdesetih izginjajo iz oglaševanja. Sodoben popotniški plakat se lahko osredotoči na najnovejše trende v ekoturizmu in varovanju kulturne dediščine, razvoju nacionalnih parkov, mednarodnih poletnih šolah, športnih tekmovanjih, tematskih izletih, etničnih festivalih.

Praktične implikacije: Avtorica prispeva k teoretičnemu razumevanju popotniškega plakata kot produkta umetniško-projektne kulture in sredstva za reprezentacijo regionalnih posebnosti. Izvedba je možna z razvojem oglasnih sporočil, izvajanjem predavanj, seminarjev, konferenc in izpopolnjevanj v turistični panogi.

Vrednost: Dobljeni rezultati poglobljajo idejo popotniških plakatov, posplošujejo njihove komunikacijske in likovno-estetske vidike ter omogočajo identifikacijo novih dejavnikov izobraževanja na konceptualni in prognostični ravni. Začrtane so bile razvojne perspektive popotniškega plakata glede na specifiko Balkana.

Ključne besede:

BALKAN TRAVEL POSTERS OF THE XX CENTURY

Abstract:

Purpose: The author considers the travel poster as a tool of advertising communications and a component of the cultural image of the Balkans. Of particular interest is cross-cultural interaction due to the expansion of info space, cultural and artistic development, and strengthening of the European integration processes.

Methodology: This study is based on system-structural, comparative and sociocultural methods. The author applied the chronological-genre principle for the analysis of visualization means and artistic-style features of travel poster in the 20th century.

Results and Conclusions: The article focuses on the analysis of the levels of stylization in posters from near realism to formalization and generalization. The visual thinking in Advertising use graphic skills, methods of visual art and stylistics of European art. Comparing the travel posters, it is shown that folk motives disappear from advertising in the 1970s. The modern travel poster can focus on the latest trends in ecotourism and protection of cultural heritage, national parks development, holding of international summer schools, sports competitions, thematic tours, ethnic festivals.

Practical implications: The author contribute to the theoretical comprehension of travel poster as a product of art-project culture and a means of representing regional specifics. The implementation is possible by developing advertising messages, conducting lecture courses, seminars, conferences, and advanced training in the tourism industry.

Value: The obtained results deepen the idea of travel posters, generalize their communicative and art-aesthetic aspects, and allow the identification of new factors of education at the conceptual and prognostic levels. The development perspectives of travel poster were outlined regarding the specifics of the Balkans.

Keywords: travel ads, poster designing, Balkans, visual stylistics, communicative design.

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¹ Department of Information Technologies and Design at the State University of Infrastructure and Technologies (Kyiv, Ukraine), Ivana Ohienka St, 19, Kyiv, Ukrajina, 02000, akademiki@ukr.net

Introduction

At the end of the 20th century, the interest in textuality changed with a new interest in visualization. Since language could not offer complete explanation of the reality, cultural philosophers increasingly emphasized the power of visual expression in art, science, and, in fact, in everyday life, where the media and communication are considered as important determinants. Appropriately, visuality requires a comprehensive analysis to integrate the methodology of cultural theory and history to interdisciplinary research. The relationship between visuality and cross-cultural communication opens up another complex area of media research with poster as one of its components.

Poster can tell much more about the age than other documents. Poster involves an instant perception of information, expressive means and deliberate layout. Cultural heritage of poster can be observed in various contexts: image, axiological, economic, semantic, and creative – as an exchange of images and symbols. Communicative approach, in our opinion, is the most appropriate for the analysis of poster stylistics within the historical framework, while cross-cultural approach adapts advertising to another cultural environment in accordance with its traditions and values, takes into account cultural differences of countries and national peculiarities of perception. The intertwining of many cultural events, changes of values, mentality and worldview led to transformations in the means of artistic expression, introduced a large number of style searches in advertising poster, particularly, in a tourist one.

Nowadays, the main contradiction lies in multiculturalism, cosmopolitanism and globalization, which are opposed by de-globalization and orientation of contemporary advertising at regional consumers. If tourist postcards with views of different countries were very popular in the second part of the 19th century and in the first part of the 20th century, though, by the middle of the 20th century, advertising poster of large and medium formats became the most common.

The purpose and objective of the research

At the beginning of the 21st century poster still remains at the forefront of main advertising medium for outdoor advertising (especially in city-lights), indoor (in the interiors for various purposes), even as an element of decoration (instead of paintings), in virtual contests of different thematic focus, and can be completely transformed into online banner ads (Pryshchenko, 2020). The relevance of this study is determined by the importance of poster in the image-cultural area of many countries, since it actively transmits social, cultural and historical development of the society, becomes pictorial chronicles and the reflection of life (Polska Szkoła Plakatu, 2007). Vitaliy Shostya, a well-known Ukrainian poster artist, stated that the view on the printed poster as an artistic phenomenon occurred in the early 19th century. Thanks to the talented personalities poster received valued artistic component as the informative content of poster and became the dominant resource in addressing the audience. At that time, exhibitions of posters as art objects after the loss of their previous utilitarian function indicated the emergence of the new kind of Art.

To reveal the Balkans advertising poster features let's examine this part of the Europe. Albania, Bulgaria (formerly Thrace, including Macedonia), Greece, Northern Macedonia, partly Romania, the European part of Turkey (Eastern Thrace), countries of former Yugoslavia (Slovenia, Montenegro, Croatia, Serbia, Northern Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina) are located on the Balkan peninsula. According to Harry Judge, the Balkans is a region with incredible nature and rich culture heritage from different ages (Judge, 2003).

Basically, East and West, Orthodox Christianity and Islam, Antiquity, Romanesque style, Gothic, Baroque and Abstractionism were actively involved in the shaping of the Balkans culture. However, the Adriatic was heavily influenced by Venice (a Latin-Byzantium hybrid). In the 9th century Serbia was more influenced by Bulgarian culture than by Byzantium, but the Byzantine and Ottoman empires had a strong impact on Bulgaria culture. Moreover, Etruscan, Greek, Byzantium, Turkish, Italian cultures dominated in the art of Montenegro in the 15th –17th centuries. After, French culture had an impact on the art of Montenegro in the 18th century and Austria-Hungary influenced it in the 19th century (The cultural monuments of Montenegro, 1997).

The outbreak of the First World War contributed to the development of national ideas, and adjusted the national character of struggle between states. National movements led to independence becoming extremely massive at that time. Specifically, it was the desire for Slavic people liberation in Austria-Hungary, Ukrainians – in the Russian Empire, Flemish – in Belgium and Irish – in the United Kingdom (Nikic 2020, p. 703).

Egidio Ivetic, the author of the book "History of the Adriatic: A Sea and its Civilization", in search of the Adriatic identity, carries out a historical tour around large ports, political and shopping centers, such as Venice, Trieste or Dubrovnik, and less-known territories, as the Adriatic is not only the sea, it is also a place of great empires battle for the influence in this region, and, finally, it's home for bright cultural diversity (Ivetic, 2021).

It's not surprisingly that cultural heritage becomes accessible to all categories of the population through advertising communications. The poster semantics expands, adds new connotations, serves for cognitive, educational and image purposes. Researchers Vasyl Sheiko and Yurii Bohutskyi believe that culture is a powerful factor in human activity. They explain that we observe the world in colours of culture, and state that mass culture is one of the most striking manifestations of modern developed societies sociocultural existence (Sheiko & Bohutskyi, 2005, p.121). Additionally, they explain the importance of cultures' dialogue in the media, since the forms of folk culture are very plastic and variable in practice (Sheiko & Bohutskyi, 2005, p. 125).

Analysing the design practice in the South of Europe, Viktor Danylenko notes that countries of this region depend on tourism for much of their income. Though, he identifies two trends in visual communications there. The researcher outlines average and internationalized, often influenced by Italian or Austrian style of visual communications in the sea coastal countries. The areas remote from the sea or large cities, on the contrary, demonstrate folk or Turkish-like elements in their visual communication and mountainous provinces show specific artistic patterns. Slovenia is the most “western” of all the Balkan countries as it is geographically close to Austria and Italy. Croatia and Montenegro have notable individual influences of European Union design activities, but often adapted to local and geographical reality. As for the urban environment of Romania, Moldova and Bulgaria – it is not remarkable, it is surrounded by media design objects in the form of endless banners and billboards with famous world brands. In general, he concludes that the Baltic countries adapt Scandinavianism, the Balkans accept Italian stylistics, and Central Europe prefers German design (Danilenko, 2009, p. 123-127).

Currently, key questions and notions of the Balkans tourism in the 20th century, including Yugoslavia, Bulgaria, Greece are not presented in literature. Therefore, this study contributes to the history of poster related to the conceptualization of visual language. Poster is considered as an object of graphic design and main advertising medium, a means of cross-cultural interaction, cultural integration and regional identification. The analysis of the artistic and style features of the Balkan region poster revealed certain trends in the depiction of tourist zones and natural objects. This study reveals the image-cultural role of travel advertising and its stylistic transformations in the Balkans.

Research methods

A number of modern scientific methods were used to solve this study issue. The author applied system-structural method as predominant to study the poster in detail, analyze its individual factors and their synthesis to highlight and analyze functional aspects of visual communication. Differentiation of the travel poster visual expressive means in past and modern times was provided with the use of comparative method. Furthermore, by applying comparative method the author contributed to understanding poster aesthetic information and art imagery, revealed significant influence of artistic styles on advertising creativity, examined compositional organization of advertising messages, specific style features, art-graphic materials and techniques. The sociocultural method made it possible to interpret advertising graphics in posters as a reflection of certain stages in society development. We applied the chronological-genre principle for the analysis of visualization means and artistic-style features of the Balkan travel posters in the 20th century.

Research results

The poster with its visual resource and the experience of specific problem solving has been and still is a desirable partner in any activity that requires a reliable communication medium with the end user, the person. It is the level of proficiency in the language of poster that allows the artist or designer to transform the information into advertising product with special characteristics of the finished creative content. Special niche belongs to the Balkan travel poster of the second part of 20th century. Advertising of goods as well as advertising of natural heritage needs creative imagery. For instance, mountains are presented on tourist posters of many countries and regions: the Balkans, Switzerland, Germany, Austria, Italy, France, Slovakia, Poland, Bulgaria, India, the United States, Crimea, the Carpathians, the Caucasus, the Ural and Tibet, providing geopolitical orientations that address issues of historical, cultural and national identity. Mountains are the subject of philosophical reflection and environmental meditation, a means of spiritual healing, scientific studies, medical therapy and recreation, as well as a source of artistic innovations. Mountains are not only the objects of reflection in art and mass media, they can also be considered as sociocultural hyper projects, influencing the view about our existence, planet Earth and society. Mountains appear on posters as romantic deserts, national parks, sports grounds, recreational resources, etc.

Travel posters of the second part of the 20th century, comparing to modern ones, are a bit naive from today's point of view, expressively straightforward, but much more creative and special. Mountains and the sea were main objects to promote tourism development. All images, coding certain messages, formed a state of reliability, stability and openness to consumers. Negative connotations and values, either as doubtful interpretations were absent in posters of the second part of the 20th century. Graphic means ranged from partial stylization of natural forms (decorative art) to emphasized geometry or pop art. Often added ethnic motives were representation of national cuisine, ethnic festivals as exotics that was interesting to Western Europeans. There was also the diversity of colours – from saturated colours to a limited colour scheme or almost monochrome solution. Accordingly, the levels of stylization in posters were from near realism to formalization and generalization. Often, compositional organization of posters was realized according to the principle of symmetry. First attempts of asymmetry in the arrangement of font and image elements of poster appeared only since the 1970s, and later. The active use of photographs instead of drawings spread at the same time.

In the days of the former Yugoslavia, advertising posters were drawn by hand, because photographing took a lot of time, and printing was not of very high quality. The design had a simple slogan, and the images showed a fusion of tradition and modernity. There are also

such tourist offers that attracted guests simply by illustrating the landscape. A good picture with the name of the place was enough to advertise the city (Nostalgija, 2014).

The selection criteria for this article were individual posters from several Balkan countries with different applied stylistics (Figure 1–Figure 5). The history of art shows that strengthening of cross-cultural communication causes the convergence of criteria for aesthetic evaluation. Additionally, specific premises appear to create peculiar local styles. Due to this, the author proves the existence of certain patterns of aesthetic evaluation for advertising objects with their own features. The unification of compositional techniques and orientation to target groups of consumers (within this topic, it was noted that tourism of the second part of the 20th century in the Balkans focused mainly on the European middle class). Travel posters demonstrate how interested potential tourists were during this period, being a common sight in travel agent offices, train stations, and airports.

Interpretation of "aesthetic – non aesthetic" remains debatable issues. The aesthetic criterion is a historically changing feature used to evaluate or classify artwork, including its decoration, painting, ideology, illusory, illustrations, kitsch, monumentality, originality, plasticity, harmony, stylization, tendency, eclecticism, expressiveness, etc. This study has confirmed identification of specific aesthetic parameters as colour and tone contrast, general colour harmony, limited colour palette, the integrity of the composition, uniqueness of the advertising idea, its clarity, the informative nature of advertising, the conciseness of textual and visual information and its structure, the presence of photo images, computer special effects and the technical quality of the performance of the advertising image. It is worth to add the presence of certain style features, including ethno stylistics in the organization of advertising space, and more precisely – their expediency in the poster. While studying advertising graphics in the context of art-project culture as a basic means of graphic design including ethno-art traditions and national colour system, it is quite appropriate to determine the aesthetic parameters of advertising objects as cultural and aesthetic, and further differentiate them with national or international principles. Colour semantics and regional imagery will be distinguished for the cultural evaluation of objects in ethno-style (Pryshchenko, 2018).

So, consider this with specific examples. The visual images of Bulgaria and Slovenia in the middle of the 20th century most fully reflect the ethnic orientation of travel posters (Figure 1-2). The travel posters of Yugoslavia are very interesting; on which it appears as a country of impregnable black mountains (Figure 3, b-c). Greece is richer in sights and symbols, but even here the classic brand has become "real Greece" – Antiquity, preserved on small islands. Later posters embody a more colourful Mediterranean image of Greece (Figure 4, c). The legendary "Orient Express" from Paris to Istanbul (then Constantinople), passing through the French, German, Austro-Hungarian and Italian railways, was supposed to become an alternative to sea cruises. True, after the First World War, the route had to be slightly changed, bypassing Austria and Germany through the Simplon Tunnel in Switzerland. Hence the updated route was named "Simplon Orient Express" (Figure 5, a). It is obviously seen that folk motives disappear from posters, as international style and/or postmodernism begins to prevail in Advertising in the 1970s, and later.

Figure 1. Bulgaria travel ads stylistics: a) 1950-60s;
b-c) 1970s - folk motives are absent (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 2. Slovenia travel ads stylistics: a) 1950-60s; b-c) 1970s - folk motives are absent (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 3. Yugoslavia travel ads stylistics: a) 1950-60s; b) 1970s, c) 1980s - folk motives are absent (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 4. Greece travel ads stylistics: a) 1940s; b) 1950s; c) 1970s - folk motives are absent (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 5. Turkish travel ads stylistics: a) 1920s;
b-c) 1970s - folk motives are absent (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Discussion

Military events and the break-up of Yugoslavia in the middle of 1990s significantly inhibited tourism and advertising of tourism in the Balkans. At the end of the twentieth century, the stylistics of the tourist poster fell under the influence of postmodernism. Due to the development and spread of computer graphics, the postmodern trend continues to develop as a conscious eclecticism at the beginning of the 21st century, which can be the subject of another article.

Stevo Nikic believes that nowadays tourism advertising with modern emphasis on ecotourism is especially interesting and promising in the context of cross-cultural interaction (Nikic, 2012). Cultural tourism is a combination of tourism-relevant activities and culture events (adventure tourism, museum, exhibition and festival tourism, preparation and servicing of national traditional dishes and drinks – the so-called gastronomic tourism (Vucetic, 2011, p. 6). The Balkans can offer a wide range of tourist services. In summer it is a beach holidays and yacht tourism on the Adriatic and Black Sea coast. Skadar Lake is the largest on the Balkan peninsula, located on the territory of Montenegro and Albania. In winter ski resorts welcome many tourists to visit numerous monasteries and churches, buy regional products or souvenirs. Therefore, visual identity is an important resource that helps to distinguish specific object, city as a tourist destination and its uniqueness.

Let's draw attention to the fact that visual elements are perceived faster, easier, more accurately, and understood by people from different countries compared to verbal language. Thus, the travel poster should comply with substantial principle of semantic integrity, which consists of physical, psychological, symbolic set with strong internal connections. Accordingly, colour elements (illustrations, syllables, brand constants of travel agencies) closely interact and determine the advertising effect. Among considerable disadvantages of travel advertising in the early 21st century the author outlines the preference for stereotyping, primitivity, the actual absence of a national image, the dominance of kitsch, eclectics, which become cultural dominants. While the main purpose of advertising is to attract the attention of potential consumer, create positive image of city, region and country, modern travel posters and their corresponding technical transformations for digital media mostly have low aesthetic level.

The analysis of image formation and art imagery issues allowed to determine the components of advertising image, in particular, for tourism. Uniqueness, aesthetics, regional specificity, compliance with the status of the tourist service and clarity to target audiences (budget, middle, premium, luxury) are examined in this study. Comparison of posters by stylistic tendencies revealed the need for more active use of creative advertising technologies: allusions, associations, allegories, hyperboles, metaphors or metonymies. "Visual metaphor becomes universal stylistic figure" (Kaftandgiev, 2012). Iis Tussyadiah looks at design thinking and how to explore and identify problems associated with the provision of tourism services and propose solutions to these problems in innovative ways. Tourism involves a wide array of services from airlines to accommodation to entertainment, but it also involves exploration of places that enables tourists to interact with objects (e.g., sceneries), people (e.g., locals), and other resources in tourism destinations. Design is getting more attention because of the relevance of design methods in the production of tourism products and services that are experiential in nature (Tussyadiah, 2014).

Following specific visual-verbal model, modern advertising message should have an artistic and semantic imagery. Lev Manovich presents a method for analysis of cultural data, with a particular focus on visual media. Cultural analytics refers to the use of computational and design methods, including data visualization, media, and interaction design, and machine learning for the exploration and analysis of contemporary culture. One goal of these explorations is to enable us to see what hundreds of millions of people around the world today create, imagine, and value (Manovich, 2020). Nowadays, visual streams prevail over verbal ones. A new fragmentary, "clip" thinking comes, based on the emotional platform and built on visibility, variability, and perception of a large number of different

visual elements. Visualization provides a basis for further analysis of images, symbols, ornaments, colours and their impact on Society through Internet banners or outdoor advertising for tourist product.

Practical implications/Original value

This study contributes to the theoretical comprehension of the travel poster as a product of art-project culture and a means of representing regional specifics, the visually orientated, and the digital in the future. Practical implementation is possible at the level of developing advertising messages, conducting lecture courses, thematic seminars and conferences for students and graduate students, and as far as advanced training courses in the tourism industry. The obtained results deepen the idea of travel posters, generalize their communicative and art-aesthetic aspects, and allow the identification of new factors of education at the conceptual and prognostic levels also.

Conclusion

The results of analytical and research work indicate that poster actively forms mass consciousness, involves into sign system, provides powerful impact on public opinion, represents past and modern creative experience. The semantic space of the poster is a visualization of significant idea, generalized reproduction of the advertised object in form and colour, perfect reflection of artifacts or natural phenomena in consciousness. Modern poster should perform perfect aesthetics, non-standard visualization and variability of graphic aids and be interesting for the target audience. Considering the poster as an effective channel of advertising communications, for the first time the idea of the visual language of the Balkan countries tourism service of the second part of the 20th century was presented. Undoubtedly, the poster plays a significant role in society, artistic practices and has a great potential for further development of tourism in the Balkans. Beyond the culture and communications, the author recognized an important relationships of the posters with society, economics, politics, and the environment.

Modern conditions establish the basis for creating peculiar local styles. Active development of the tourism, the use of the aesthetic potential of natural harmony will contribute to the approval of national identity, creative thinking development and improvement of the visual and info space. The travel poster can focus on the latest trends in ecotourism and protection of cultural heritage, national parks development, holding of international summer schools for students, sports competitions, thematic tours, ethnic festivals, etc. Within the framework of the designated vector of research, a special place is supposed to be given to further search and comparative analysis of semantic roots in the use of pictorial elements and colouring of the Balkan region in order to develop cross-cultural communications in currently.

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